

Life cycle definition and description

Deliverable 8.1

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Lead Partner: ITENE

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The SCALIBUR project aims to demonstrate new valorization routes, such as biobased products, for urban biowaste. Therefore, SCALIBUR enables the formation of a partnership which includes waste management companies, technology developers, researchers and end users; to recover and transform biowaste from three municipalities, Madrid (ES), Albano (IT), and Kozani (EL), into value added products. These new value chains will transform HORECA waste into proteins, lipids and chitin from insect rearing, while the organic fraction of MSW will be hydrolyzed into sugars that will be further converted into biopesticides and bioplastics by fermentation. Moreover, the resulting biogas from MSW and USS will be upgraded by bioelectrochemical treatment to produce commodity chemicals and bioplastics.

SCALIBUR will create new business models for the resulting circular value chains, applying a sustainable approach to generate new activities and benefits. Therefore, the sustainability of all technological processes must be assessed. This evaluation will include techno-economical, environmental and social levels. Environmental impacts are going to be analyzed through the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) as well as the Social level. The technological developments will be analyzed under an engineering-oriented approach for the techno-economic assessment of the developed processes.

The deliverable 8.1, is the first one from WP8, and it refers to the definition and the description of the initial settings, the methodology and boundaries to be used for the environmental, techno-economic, social impacts and safety assessment. The life cycle and safety assessment of the WP8 will give information about the sustainability approaches followed in WPs4-6 for the selected waste streams.

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